

NEW INTERNET RESOURCES AS A TOOL
FOR TEACHING A NON-NATIVE LANGUAGE

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S.A.Adilova

*Ph.D. Associate Professor of the Department of General Linguistics
TSPU named after Nizami*

Annotation: *The article deals with such relatively new Internet resources as Web 2.0 technologies. The author provides a definition of such resources, types and ways of their use when teaching a non-native language in higher educational institutions.*

Keywords: *applied linguistics, language teaching methods, teaching a foreign language, Web 2.0 technologies, multimedia, educational blog.*

INTRODUCTION

Web 2.0 is a Web of the second generation, it consists of a kind of sites where online content is created by users themselves. The content of Web 2.0 sites is mostly created and managed by users. Web 2.0 sites are controlled more by interactive tools than publishing tools. Content creation and promotion of Web 2.0 resources takes place by the audience using interactive tools, and not by means of publication as in Web 1.0. Social networks, social bookmarks, online games, blogs, forums, communities, groups, comments, chats, and other Web 2.0 elements and resources take precedence over traditional sites and content methods.

The use of Web 2.0 technologies is also one of the ways to use information computer technologies in foreign language classes. Traditional pedagogical technologies today no longer ensure the complete assimilation of an ever-increasing amount of information, and the rapid updating of educational material and the need to master a large flow of information require completely new principles and teaching methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Computer technologies have many advantages over traditional teaching methods, as they integrate audiovisual information of any form (text, sound, graphics, animation, etc.) [1]. The use of electronic forms of teaching materials is convenient and efficient. Other advantages of ICT should be noted here: ease of use, accessibility, interactivity, multimedia, visibility and security. In this regard, Web 2.0 technologies have significant potential in the formation of intercultural competence of future foreign language specialists, namely:

- in accelerating the pace of classes and increasing motivation to study foreign languages and cultures due to the visual presentation of educational material and strengthening its emotional component;

- in ensuring the effectiveness of independent work, allowing each student to choose the best way and pace of mastering the educational material;
- in the ability to organize and lead discussions on professional topics by participating in online communities, blogs, etc.;
- in providing prompt access to the information of interest [2].

Web 2.0 is a platform of social services and services that allows a wide range of Internet users not only to receive information, but also to be its creators and co-authors. All materials with which students work are scooped from the Internet. The main advantage of Web 2.0 technologies is that they allow you to store data on specially designed web services, which ensures their availability [3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Currently, Web 2.0 technologies are widely used by young people for entertainment and information purposes. And this is obvious, because they are frequent users of the media space. It is also clear that the younger generation is trying to enter the computer world through their own stay in the network, organizing and involving their peers of interest in communicative communities, thus modeling the system of Internet technologies. Nowadays, it is possible to be on the World Wide Web using a mobile phone, doing a lot of operations, which gives the right to talk about the indirect involvement of young people in new information technologies. Thus, our younger generation is growing up in a digital world, where they know from the "diaper" how to turn on and off the computer, how to use a mobile phone, remote control, etc. Consequently, the youth of the 21st century are well adapted to changes in computer technology, which suggests an excellent opportunity to use Web 2.0 for educational purposes.

Before involving students directly in the process of teaching a foreign language using the possibilities of Web 2.0 technologies, it is necessary to investigate the relevance of the problems of using Internet resources by young people for entertainment purposes in order to obtain a more effective work result. Namely:

1. What Web 2.0 resources are most commonly used by students?
2. How often do students use the Internet for personal and educational purposes?
3. How do they evaluate the copyright of the materials they find?
4. What did they personally create on the Internet and for what purpose?
5. How often do they communicate online and in real life with potential members of communication communities?

There are different opinions regarding the use of Web 2.0 in education. However, some aspects of the introduction of Internet technologies are indisputable, which have a beneficial effect both on the learning process and on each individual student individually.

According to experts, there are several areas where web 2.0 technologies can be implemented: research activities, language literacy, collaboration, and publications.

Web 2.0 tools allow students to use new ways of doing research. Web 2.0 technologies create new data organization structures in the Internet environment, new sources, forms and tools for requesting information in the vast computer world. All this

inspires the student to be an independent researcher, but also causes problems for him and the teacher.

This aspect aims to improve a certain attitude towards the language. The interaction of language with writing is key in this situation. In writing, students learn to express their thoughts correctly, to express themselves clearly. The computerization of the sphere of communications has demonstrated to society the need for a high level of foreign language proficiency, especially in telecommunication networks, where the ability to exchange written or oral messages in real time without intermediaries is necessary. Conducting a spontaneous professional conversation with native speakers orally or, even more difficult, in writing, implies a high level of knowledge of the language, active possession of it.

It should be noted that for students involved in the process of learning a foreign language using digital technologies, the curriculum for the discipline should be drawn up taking into account the development of language literacy skills, increasing motivation for creative research and developing critical thinking skills.

The key to using Web 2.0 technologies is to ensure communication between users. These tools allow students on the common infrastructure of the Internet to agree on collaborative solutions and implement them. Web 2.0 technologies offer students a set of tools that allow them to support forms of learning that involve the organization of joint projects to solve assigned problems.

This type of activity is a consequence of the need to write original material that is different from others in the group. Web 2.0 provides tools and an audience. It is easy to see all the activities of the group in the class on the monitor display, at least it is useful at the initial stage of training. The Web 2.0 space gives you the confidence to create your own project, different from others in the group.

Therefore, the four aspects presented above define a number of possibilities for introducing Web 2.0 technologies into the educational process.

The introduction of Web 2.0 to education seems promising. Moreover, a community of energetic professionals is currently working to promote the use of Web 2.0 technologies in education.

The main reason should be that the younger generation is already involved in the use of Web 2.0 technologies. Students who already have experience in communicating on the Internet will have fewer difficulties in learning using information and computer technologies.

There are two other reasons for introducing Web 2.0 into education. The use of Web 2.0 technologies in teaching a foreign language allows, firstly, to achieve a certain level of foreign language competence during the period of study at a university, and secondly, to improve the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in subsequent professional activities.

The use of Web 2.0 for learning opens up wide opportunities for the development of a fundamentally new form of independent learning, which under these conditions becomes organized, controlled and adaptable to the individual characteristics of the student. The computerization of teaching foreign languages is intended, first of all, to create psychologically comfortable conditions for the effective assimilation of the material.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we note the need and ease of use of Web 2.0 technologies in education, which reinforce their importance with the main components: the organization of work on the Internet and the motivation of students to study the discipline at the university. The practical use of Web 2.0 technologies will contribute to meaningful saturation of the space of collective mental activity and the transition from the model of activating education to the model of open activating education, thereby ensuring the quality of education.

The use of Web 2.0 technologies can help language teachers solve one of the most significant problems in teaching foreign languages outside the language environment - the problem of forming language skills. Providing students with the opportunity to receive, consolidate and activate the introduced material in the self-study mode, using a computer, helps to improve the quality of education.

REFERENCES:

1. Zakharova I.G. Information technologies in education: Proc. allowance for students. higher textbook establishments. 3rd ed., ster. M.: Publishing Center "Academy", 2007. 192 p.
2. Fundamentals of tutor activity in the system of distance education: Specialized training course / S.A. Shchennikov, A.G. Teslinov, A.G. Chernyavskaya et al. // Information technologies in education. 2nd ed., rev. M.: Drofa, 2006. 591 p.
3. Bennett S., Maton K., Kervin L. The 'digital natives' debate: A critical review of the evidence // British journal of educational technology. 2008. Doi:10.1111/j. 1467-8535.200700793.x.
4. Shulgina E.M. Project approach in teaching foreign languages at the present stage. – <http://refoteka.ru/r-136935.html>.
5. Azhel Yu.P. Using Web 2.0 technologies in teaching foreign languages // Young scientist (electronic scientific journal). - 2012. - No. 6. - P. 369–371. – <http://www.moluch.ru/archive/41/4967/>.
6. Sysoev P.V., Evstigneev M.N. Modern educational Internet resources in teaching a foreign language // Foreign languages at school. - 2008. - No. 6. - P. 3–10.
7. European system of levels of foreign language proficiency. – http://lenda-center.ru/evropeyskaya_shkala_yazy.
8. Filatova A.V. Optimization of teaching foreign languages through blog technologies for students of language specialties of universities. - Dis. ... cand. ped. Sciences. - M., 2009. - S. 52–95.